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Influence of Capacity Building on Effectiveness of Teaching-Learning Process among Public Senior Secondary School Teachers in Adamawa State, Nigeria

Magaji, S. A.¹

Egbebi, J. O.¹

Deyin Hyelanaati Levi¹

Dauda, A. G.²

abduldauda444@gmail.com

08065611721

¹Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

²Department of Vocational & Technical Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Abstract

The study examined the Influence of Capacity Building on Effectiveness in Teaching-Learning Process Among Public Secondary School Teachers in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study had 2 specific objectives research questions and null hypotheses. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study is 7161 senior secondary school teachers during 2023/2024 session. The sample size was 716 teachers. A self-developed structured questionnaire titled “Capacity Building and Teachers’ Effectiveness (CBTE) was used as instrument for the study. The questionnaire was validated by experts in the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum and experts from the Measurement and Evaluation Section, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The reliability index was 0.79 and the data collected were analyzed using frequency, percentages, and mean scores to answer research questions. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test all the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that among others that capacity building influences teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tools through training, on the use of computers, posters, projectors, audio-visual materials, use of chalkboards and printed materials in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria (p-value=.143). The study concluded that capacity building has the ability to influence teachers’ effectiveness in teaching-learning process through the ability to use instructional materials, teachers’ method of teaching and teachers’ ability to reinforce learners as effective teaching tools in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. It was recommended that Adamawa state Government should brace up teachers’ capacity building on use of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Adamawa State Ministry of Education should collaborate with Secondary school authorities at intervals to organize teachers’ capacity-building trainings on current teaching instructional techniques for effective teaching and learning in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Keyword: Capacity Building, Teaching-Learning Process, Secondary School Teachers

Introduction

Capacity building has become a popular concept in the education sector across both developed and emerging economies. Capacity building refers to the process through which individuals or organizations acquire, enhance, and sustain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment, and other resources necessary to perform their roles effectively or expand their capabilities (Kumari, 2022). Additionally, it involves the allocation and investment of resources—whether physical, intellectual, or human—particularly in situations where other variables have failed within specific institutional or social contexts. A systematic emphasis on capacity building within educational programs often highlights underlying imbalances in the sector. Ideally, capacity building should proactively serve as a fundamental component of efforts to strengthen social institutions and create conducive conditions for teachers in the school system to deliver optimal performance (Egbo, 2011).

However, teaching is a versatile field that requires, always, the correct identification of teaching methods, self-development, and training. The role of teachers necessitates a continuous pursuit of updated knowledge across various

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disciplines, including the acquisition of current skills, training, and information aligned with acceptable standards of general studies, with ICT being a crucial component. Globally, improving teacher education programs remains a priority, particularly in developing nations, as the quality of education and the progress of a nation are directly tied to the caliber of its teachers (Adeosun, 2018). In Nigeria, the objectives of teacher education include fostering a spirit of inquiry and creativity among teachers while equipping them with the intellectual and professional foundations needed for their responsibilities. This preparation also aims to enable teachers to adapt to evolving circumstances, as outlined by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014). The policy underscores that teacher education must account for changes in methods and curricula, ensuring that educators are regularly exposed to innovations in their field. Consequently, professional teacher training is structured into two key phases: pre-service and in-service training, with specific institutions tasked with the responsibility of delivering these programs.

Teachers who demonstrate high levels of effectiveness are more inclined to adopt and apply innovative teaching strategies, implement management techniques that foster student autonomy, establish realistic goals, and persevere when students struggle. They also go the extra mile to support low-achieving students and design instructional approaches that enhance students' self-confidence in their academic abilities (Silverman, 2019). Such teachers are instrumental in creating a learning environment where students can thrive academically and personally. The foundation of teacher effectiveness lies in thorough lesson preparation, beginning with crafting a comprehensive lesson plan. A lesson plan serves as the teacher's roadmap, outlining what students need to learn and detailing the most effective methods to achieve this within the available class time. Without a well-prepared plan, delivering a lesson effectively becomes challenging. As Ahievboloria (2015) highlights, a successful lesson plan should seamlessly incorporate three essential components: clearly defined objectives for student learning, engaging teaching and learning activities, and strategic methods to assess student understanding. These elements ensure that lessons are structured, impactful, and conducive to achieving desired learning outcomes.

Statement of the Research Problem:

In general, workers are expected to do well in their jobs, but the need for an enabling environment is not being given the priority it deserves. The situation is even worse in the teaching profession where society feels that teachers are owed nothing. The way teachers teach have direct impact on the learning outcomes. Therefore, it is important that teachers are expected and encouraged to be trained and retrained after employment for the achievement of teaching effectiveness in the discharge of their duties during teaching-learning process in the classroom. Training and retraining programs, which should be prioritized by government authorities and school managers, are often overlooked or inadequately addressed. Egbebi (2024) quoting the address of Universal Basic Education Commission, UBEC, as posited by Executive Secretary of the Commission confirmed that 57 billion naira was disbursed for teachers' training in 13 years from 2009-2022, having noted a few number of teachers that had undergone training in recent years. He affirmed that the UBEC 2022 National Personnel Audit revealed that 67.5 percent of teachers in public schools and 86.3 percent in private schools have not been given the privilege of attending in-service training in the last five years (2018-2022). This is expected to have negative implication for quality education impartation in the UBE programme. This indicates that the current training arrangements for teachers are severely insufficient to meet the requirements outlined in the UBE Acts of 2004. More so, this development will affect the quality of learning outcomes at almost every education level if this research is not conducted. This has led to a lack of morale and inability to adapt to changes and innovations in the educational system of senior public secondary education. The existed issues on instructional material supplies; students' and teachers' motivation; teacher preparation capacity, instructional management strategies, and teacher communication patterns. All these put together are faced with one kind of challenge or the other ranging from inadequate capacity building of teachers' effectiveness in the system.

In recent years, basic education has been a primary focus for the Federal Government and key stakeholders, including the international community. However, senior secondary education, an essential level within the education system, appears to be falling short of its intended objectives. Student retention rates at this level remain low, and those who manage to graduate often exhibit subpar communication skills and a lack of moral virtues. Additionally, many dropouts from this educational level are involved in social vices such as pickpocketing, hawking, scavenging, street begging, and even violent activities like suicide bombing. These issues point to a potential deficiency in the effectiveness of secondary school teachers in fulfilling their teaching responsibilities. Given that teacher effectiveness is indispensable to the success of any school system, it is reasonable to infer that teachers play a role in the current challenges faced by senior secondary school education. This study, therefore, seeks to examine the Influence of Capacity Building on Effectiveness in the Teaching-Learning Process among Public Senior Secondary School Teachers in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

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Objectives of the Study

1. Assess the influence of capacity building on teachers’ instructional materials usage as teaching effectiveness tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the influence of capacity building on teachers’ method of teaching as tool of teaching effectiveness in the study area.

Research Questions

1. Does the capacity building training have any influence on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as tool of teaching effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria?
2. In what ways does capacity building influence teachers’ methods of teaching as tool of teaching effectiveness in the study area?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the opinions of principals, teachers, and Ministry of Education Officials (MOE) on the influence of capacity building efforts on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents on the influence of capacity building training on teachers’ methods of teaching as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in the study area.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design with population of this study was 7,161 respondents, consisting of 6,709 teachers, 415 principals, and 37 Ministries of Education Officials and sample size of 716 consisting of 671 teachers, 41 principals, and 4 MOE officials. The instrument used for collecting data for this study was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher titled “Capacity Building and Teachers’ Effectiveness (CBTE). The instrument consisted of two sections; Section A consists of the demography of the respondents while Section B showed questions that were adopted to elicit answers from respondents in the research questions on the Influence of Capacity Building on Public Senior Secondary School Teacher Effectiveness in Teaching-Learning Process in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The researcher collected a letter of introduction from the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum. Then, an official visit was made to schools selected in Adamawa State. The researcher and three research assistants were showed introductory letters to principals of sampled schools in their respective locations in the State in readiness for the collection of data. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the data analysis. The responses that were obtained from the questionnaires were tallied and coded, analyzed and presented using descriptive and inferential statistics. In the descriptive statistics, frequency counts and percentages and mean were used to answer the research questions, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance because the normality test showed that the data was normally distributed, and the categories of respondents were there (principals, teachers, and MOE officials).

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: Does the capacity building training have any influence on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as tool of teaching effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on influence of capacity building training on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Capacity Building and Teachers’ use of Instructional materials	3.8	.560	Has Influence

Fieldwork, (2024)

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The analysis of items used to answer research questions 1 revealed calculated grand mean of 3.8 greater than the benchmark of 3.0. This indicates that principal, teachers and MOE officials agreed that through capacity building training, teachers use instructional materials effectively in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: In what ways does capacity building influence teachers’ methods of teaching as tool of teaching effectiveness in the study area?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on influence of capacity building training on teachers’ method of teaching

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Capacity Building and Teachers’ use of Instructional materials	3.6	.251	Has Influence

Fieldwork, (2024)

The analysis of items used to answer research questions 2 revealed calculated grand mean of 3.8 greater than the benchmark of 3.0. This indicates that principal, teachers and MOE officials agreed that through capacity building training, teachers make effective use methods of teaching in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1

Table 3: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Influence of Capacity Building on Teachers’ Ability to use Instructional Materials as Effective Teaching Tool in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	.196	2	.127	2.12	.143	Retained
Within Groups	28.002	714	.048			
Total	28.198	716				

Fieldwork, (2024)

The analysis of the results in Table 3 shows differences in the opinions of respondents (principal, teachers and MOE officials) on the influence of capacity building efforts on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The result reveals a calculated F value of 2.12 at a significant p-value of .143. Since the calculated p-value of .143 is more than the fixed probability level of 0.05 ($P > 0.05$), the null hypothesis is therefore retained which means that there is no differences in the opinions of respondents (principal, teachers and MOE officials) on the influence of capacity building efforts on teachers’ ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

Table 4: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Influence of Capacity Building Training on Teachers’ Method of Teaching as Effective Teaching Tool in Public Senior Secondary Schools in the Study Area

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	.106	2	.133	1.210	.318	Retained
Within Groups	30.617	714	.064			
Total	30.723	716				

Fieldwork, (2024)

The analysis of the results in Table 4 shows differences in the opinions of respondents (principal, teachers and MOE officials) on the influence of capacity building training on teachers’ method of teaching as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in the study area. The result reveals a calculated F value of 1.210 at a significant p-value of .318. Since the calculated p-value of .318 is more than the fixed probability level of 0.05 ($P > 0.05$), the null hypothesis is therefore retained

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which means that there is no differences in the opinions of respondents on the influence of capacity building training on teachers' method of teaching as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

Capacity building influences teachers' ability to use instructional materials as effective teaching tool through training, on use of computers, posters, projectors, audio-visual materials, use of chalkboards and printed materials in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The test of hypothesis showed no significant differences in the opinions of respondents (p -value=.143). This finding is in accordance with the report of Dittimiya (2015) who reported that instructional materials in secondary schools are the resources used to help the teacher to make the teaching and learning process easier. Instructional materials include both visuals, audio visuals and electronic interactives such as real objects, film strips, pictures, flashcards, posters, maps, charts, graphs, tape recorders, radio, video, television, computers, slide projectors, projector, and over-head projectors among others. This was supported by the researcher that adequate provision of instructional materials in secondary schools in Adamawa state ensures more effective teaching and learning since the learner not only hears but also sees and does while the knowledge of a wide variety of instructional materials and the specific functions, they can perform is a value-added advantage for the teacher. The researcher further opines that teachers should endeavour to use as many instructional materials provided as possible and in cases where they are inadequate instructional materials, improvisation can substitute.

Capacity building influences teachers' method of teaching as effective teaching tool through training, on use of lecture method, discussion, demonstration, discovery, project, fieldtrip method as well as cooperative/collaborative strategies in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The test of hypothesis showed no significant differences in the opinions of respondents (p -value=.318). The findings of this study align with Ibrahim's (2001) assertion that teaching methods are a set of principles and strategies employed by teachers to facilitate student learning. These methods are shaped both by the subject matter and the nature of the learners. For a teaching method to be deemed appropriate and effective, it must consider the learner's characteristics, the content being taught, and the specific type of learning intended. Teaching approaches can be broadly categorized into teacher-centered and student-centered models.

In a teacher-centered (authoritarian) approach, the teacher holds the primary authority and is responsible for delivering content through lectures and direct instruction. Students are often seen as passive recipients of knowledge, and their learning is predominantly assessed through tests and exams. In this model, teaching and assessment are typically treated as distinct, with learning outcomes primarily measured through objective assessments.

Conclusion

The study concluded that capacity building has the ability to influence teachers' ability to use instructional materials, teachers' method of teaching and teachers' ability to reinforce learners as effective teaching tool in public senior secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The study recommended that The Secondary School Authorities should establish structured mentorship programs where experienced teachers can mentor new or underperforming teachers. Peer learning initiatives should also be encouraged to foster collaborative learning among teachers and help them adopt best practices.

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